

Formidlingsaktivitet

Art: STEM/STEAM science communication.

Sted: Svendborg Gymnasium

Skole: Svendborg Gymnasium, 1.g & 2.g & 3.g elever

Dato: 07. march 2024.

Tid: 14:00 – 17:00.

Antal elever: 7 – 9 (some left after 90 minutes).

GDPR / pictures for public? Yes. Permission obtained.

Lærerkontakt: Rune Høirup Madsen & Mads Fjeldvig Gammeltoft

Formidler: Tobias C. Hinse & Mattias Ermakov Thing (Syddansk Universitet, FKF / SDU-Galaxy).

March 7, 2024 15:26

March 7, 2024 15:17

March 7, 2024 15:18

